

A Performance of *Ruddhoshongeet* by Bratyojon in New Delhi

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This review of Ruddhoshongeet was composed by the present writer following a performance of the play on January 20, 2010 at Kamani Auditorium, New Delhi, at the Bharat Rang Mahotsav organized by National School of Drama.

The Bengalis living outside Bengal had been hearing about *Ruddhoshongeet* for the last one year, and some of them happened to read the play in one of the sharodiya potrikas. But for the first time the Bengalis of Delhi were fortunate enough to witness a performance of this play that became a phenomenon in the contemporary Bengali stage on 20 January 2010, at Kamani Auditorium, New Delhi, as a part of Bharat Rang Mahotsav organized by National School of Drama.

There was a kiosk outside the entrance to the auditorium selling the publications of Bratyojon and books by Bratya Basu. The tired theatre-worker said that Bratyojon directly came to the playhouse after arriving at Delhi by train from Bhopal where they put up a performance of *Ruddhoshongeet* also as a part of Bharat Rang Mahotsav, though the superlative performance later on betrayed no sign of that sheer fatigue which they must have endured.

The audience constituted of the usual lot of *kaalcharal* Bongs, who are mostly menopausal bhadraloks and senile govt officers and their relatives, so obviously some of the play's anti-establishment dialogues were not cheered the way some of the directly anti-CPI/CPM statements were applauded. But nevertheless, they loved the play, and were enthralled by the performance and did not want to leave the playhouse even after the play was over with the hope of hearing a word or two from Bratya himself when the entire cast came on stage. The playhouse was packed with spectators, though most of them, unlike the regular Kolkata theatre aficionado, earned their place in the audience by virtue of possessing a 'pass' without ever bothering to buy tickets.

Now, coming straight to a discussion of the performance of *Ruddhoshongeet*: this play is

about the the life and times of the singer Debabrata Biswas (his autobiography was titled *Bratyojoner Ruddhoshongeet*, i.e., 'the stifled song of the outcast') who was victimized by the 'Tagorean' establishment called Visva Bharati for allegedly taking liberties in his renderings of Robindroshongeet. The first thing that strikes us is the fluent performance of Debshankar Haldar in the role of Debabrata Biswas who acts as a pivot in the entire structure of the play. Bratya Basu playing the double roles of two despots, Promod Dasgupta and Santosh Kumar Ghosh, representing the two most powerful and hegemonic establishments of Bengal left politics and Anandabazar Patrika, was the *piece de resistance* of the play. A rebellious and conscientious artist tyrannized by these establishments was portrayed brilliantly by Satrajit Sarkar who played Ritwik Ghatak. It appeared that Rajorshi Dey's (who used to play Salil Choudhury) departure from the group (as he recently went to Hyderabad to join a popular television network) affected the play. The actor playing Salil Chowdhury, in spite of his honest and flawless acting and his physical resemblance with the late maestro, was not convincing enough for the role.

Sabyasachi Chattopadhyay played a minor role, that of Jyoti Basu (who happens to be one of *the* major characters in the history of twentieth century Bengal), but naturally such a character grabs attention if not for any other reason, then for the sheer weight of this persona oppressively felt by generations of Bengalis born and grown up during his regime. The actor might have done well in not overdoing the parting remark of Jyotibabu (*aami abar culture-fulture bujhi na*, to be translated as: Well, I do not understand these culture thingies), which in any case surely would have brought applause. The striking physical resemblance (barring the height, the actor was taller than Jyotibabu) was interesting; however, the mannerism of Jyoti Basu was missing to some extent, as the leader's casual, broken syntax was lacking, and the Jyoti Basu type composure and indifference (even say callousness) were not seen. Jyoti Basu and Promod Dasgupta represent the two most important figures of the hegemonic left movement in Bengal, and the playwright-director-actor Bratya must be credited

for taking the rhino by its two horns.

Bratya Basu and the entire cast of the play being felicitated by the Director, NSD after the performance

This play is Debshankar Haldar's spectacular show of acting prowess. The spotlight is on him, and naturally he is most loved by the audience. Doelpakhi Dasgupta's Manjushree and Sushmita Goswami's Suchitra are impressive, and it was certainly not easy to share the stage-space with Debshankar without getting overshadowed by his character, so the performances of Sushmita and Doelpakhi were even more creditworthy.

The songs of this play were on the stage performances (real instant singing, not recorded) which gave them a raw vitality: they were indicative of the times when Bengal underwent a great intellectual and political ferment and related to the contemporary period when an equally passionate anti-CPM struggle has been launched in different aspects of Bengali life.

Unto the background, throughout the performance, there was a gigantic empty rectangular photo-frame (not upright, but slightly tilted, about 10 degrees from the ground), hung from the ceiling by what looked like a long ragged sheet of clothes. That could very well be symbolic of the construction of the play out of diverse threads (evidently the playwright has undertaken great pains

in researching for this play, particularly where he raids the headquarters itself, i.e., when he reproduces Communist Party's trial of Ritwik Ghatak on stage), while the empty frame stood for an abstract perspective/aperture, its tiltedness being quite suggestive. Among other things, it suggests the tiltedness of the entire IPTA movement, and its emptying out.

This play's politics is Foucauldian. It is a critique of power, authority and establishment. The twentieth century Marxist experiments in the exercise of state power have been disastrous to say the least, and a liberal-anarchist trend believes that this has been due to the fact that the very nature of power is oppressive, and leftists in power everywhere ended up becoming a new privileged class. The Communist party structure has been fascistic since Lenin, and a communist party is as egalitarian an apparatus as Anandabazar or Visva-Bharati. Hence, the promise of revolution soon ends in disillusionment, slogans end in jargons, proclamations in hypocrisy and commitments in opportunism. The dissenter either has to surrender or has to bear the brunt, like Meyerhold had to, under Stalin's regime.

The play's statement has no ambiguity. The honest, conscientious and committed artist makes a series of daring decisions, not only refusing to align with establishment (thus bordering on the playwright's own trajectory), but challenging and taking on the establishments again and again. This individual crusade has some strong revolutionary implications for the society, and its precisely where the play presents the spirited aesthetics of a rebel artist and itself attains the uncompromising dissent of an artwork (a work of art being essentially non-conformist, defamiliarization being one of the supreme conditions of art). As Hemingway wrote in *Old Man and the Sea*, the rebel protagonist of the play seems to hold that a man can be destroyed but not defeated.

Here the play ends. but where does the answer to oppression lie? How is a change possible? Or, in other words, the point is to change the world, not merely to interpret it.

A change of society, as we have learnt it the hard way, is not what a Stalin, a Promod Dasgupta, or a Charu Majumdar can offer us. Instead, they all perpetrate the old power structures which they superficially fight against. We have to look for the answer elsewhere. And it is interesting to note that Bengal in recent times started to search for answers beyond the various hues of left doctrines, which is nothing short of an epistemic break, and for which Bratya Basu's theatre has been responsible in a considerable way. The rebel Robindroshongeeet artist Debabrata Biswas is an example of what Gramsci called organic intellectuals, who have the intuition to throw their weight behind emerging popular aspirations and new kinds of struggles (as opposed to traditional intellectuals who stick to received wisdom), and if we may be allowed to extend this category, we may note that the rebel playwright-director Bratya Basu himself is an example of an organic intellectual who was ostracized by his then theatre group for going to the annual public meeting of Trinomool Congress on 21 July in 2007, at a time when it was almost suicidal for any Bengali intellectual to share a public stage with the woman who challenged the authority of Left Front. The artist/thinker/revolutionary who challenges status quo may suffer immediately, but the people and posterity might have other plans for such a figure. Debabrata Biswas was an organic intellectual; he continues to be one of the most loved icons Bengalis ever had, irrespective of the numerous attempts of the establishments to gag him.

Perhaps the only way to destroy the oppressive hegemony of establishments and authorities is to effectively empower the masses. The failure of Bengal renaissance might be at the core of Bengal's ailments. The upper caste – upper class consensus has resulted in that “breathless, nauseating” (to quote Salil Chowdhury from the play) atmosphere of the social-cultural-political scenario, which is a fertile ground for establishments to grow into omnipotence. But a question arises precisely here: is not this play also a part of that elitist sublime of Bengali identity, that is centred around a giant like

Tagore himself, and his songs? Intellectual giants, creative geniuses, upper class dissenters fighting against equally upper class oppressors and establishments; do we actually get out of that?

In group theatre, an actor often has to play more than one role in such plays as these, which come with a huge cast. Interestingly, Tanmay Sur plays the minor roles of a bare-bodied dancer at IPTA function and the servant of Debabrata (George) Biswas, while he also plays poet Subhash Mukhopadhyay. Compared to Bratya's portrayal of two establishment figures, I find this combining act (might be purely contingent) rather unnerving. Come to think of this: a subaltern and a brahmin, a servant and a poet; is not the gap too glaring to ridicule our liberal and/or communistic convictions?

No simple answer. Let's ask uncomfortable questions.

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